

D2.1 Website and Repository

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1. Introduction

SPEAR will be supporting the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), specifically for its nine implementing universities (SPEAR's six implementing partners (IPs) and three supporting and implementing partners (SIPs)). SPEAR offers supportive structures comprised in its interconnected Community of Learning (CoL) and Community of Practice (CoP). CoL will provide learning platforms while CoP provides an arena for experience exchanges. Both these are crucial to successful and sustainable implementation of GEPs, a key instrument to improving gender equality. Beyond the project, the tools, methodology and recommendations developed during SPEAR will be useful to wider communities of GE-practitioners in the EU.

SPEAR's central objective is to implement GEPs in its nine implementing RPOs. Based on a step-by-step guide to GEP implementation devised by the European Institute for Gender Equality, SPEAR follows a distinct methodological path committed to creative, open, mitigating, processual, accountable, SMART and sustainable changes (SPEAR's COMPASS).

In this context, the SPEAR website and learning repository is aimed at serving as the primary online platform for communication, both within the consortium and with the public, while in parallel acting as a gateway to key SPEAR deliverables and outcomes, including the integrated learning repository of the project. The website of the project has already been launched (earlier than planned), containing basic information on the project and its expected outcomes as well as valuable information and resources from the gender equality domain. The development has been undertaken by Europa Media (technical development and administration) with the cooperation of all partners (content development).

With the above in mind, the current document, titled "D2.1: SPEAR Website and Repository", aims at introducing the reader to the SPEAR website and learning repository and its design (Chapter 2), before providing meaningful information about its structure (Chapter 3), its monitoring procedures (Chapter 4) and finally, about its future development (Chapter 5).

2. SPEAR Website and Repository

2.1 Objectives

The SPEAR Website and Learning Repository has to fulfill different objectives.

The objective is to develop a user-friendly and interactive website acting as a virtual dissemination vehicle, providing the general public and specific target groups access to valuable information. Information on the project's objectives and results will be widely disseminated in web campaigns to have maximum cross-sectoral impact.

Another objective is to provide a closed interaction forum for SPEAR's partners, particularly for the exchanges, meetings and document sharing of Learning Support Clusters (LSC). The technological solution has to take into consideration the functionalities of discussions, sharing documents and working on the same material by more people.

As the Grant Agreement's Annex I states: „*The purpose is to equip change agents with sufficient knowledge for consulting researchers and teachers interested in this dimension of GE practice. SPEAR sets out to engage S/IPs' teachers and researchers in this topic, and its focus on raising their awareness and motivation will be supplemented with actual training and dissemination in Communities of Learning (CoL) activities, e.g. on aspects and possibilities of gendered innovations. SPEAR will thus develop learning materials and organize webinars on the topic of strengthening and integrating the gender dimension in research content, research proposals and teaching curricula.*” SPEAR learning repository has to support this impact.

2.2 Technical specifications

The SPEAR website will introduce the learning materials in an attractive, user-friendly manner that allows also users to send us feedback or interact in other ways. EM is responsible for finding the technical solution, using its own Content management system CMS (nJinn – overall system; nGrosser - website) and Learning management system LMS (nStructor) solutions.

nStructor is a learning management system for E-learning courses powered by nJinn, a PHP-based application framework developed by EMG, the mother company of Europa Media.

Part of the solution described below has been developed within the framework of the INNO-4-AGRI FOOD H2020 project N° 681482, supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The visitor front end is a HTML5 web application using a responsive layout based on Bootstrap 3 framework which guarantees that the application is efficiently scaled and displayed well on every device including tablets and smartphones.

The software uses jQuery on client-side which requires JavaScript to be enabled. The application supports all the major desktop browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari 5.1+, IE 10+, Edge, Opera), mobile clients (iOS, Android) and does not require any plugins to be installed.

The system manages multiple user roles and allows administrators to invite lecturers who then can set up and manage the digital content. The system supports the material to be publicly available. However, some functions, like individual progress tracking, are only available for those courses that require registration. This is why SPEAR has decided to require the registration from all users. The publicly available content will be accessible through GenPORT.

In case of courses that are available after registration the system stores information about the users' 'completion' status and allow them to suspend and resume watching the content. Results of exercises corresponding to the modules and chapters are also be stored in user accounts. The application has a stateless, RESTful Web API using a cookie-based authentication system. The authentication system relies on a cascade encryption algorithm that ensures high level of security. Personal data of E-learning participants is duly protected.

2.2.1 Chapter

Presentations and other material can be organised under chapters or other sub-sections that group content from a thematic perspective. Chapters have their own description and additional supporting material can be attached to them. Chapters are also the first level of completion status evaluation: completed presentations and quizzes are registered on the chapters' level.

2.2.2 Module

Chapters that belong to larger thematic areas can optionally be represented in modules where progress indicators on chapter level are aggregated.

2.2.3 Exams

Custom quizzes and exams can be added to chapters using multiple question types like single and multiple-choice questions. Optionally exams can be a condition of a chapter's or module's completion. Exams can also be published as a SCORM-compliant presentation. However, SPEAR does not plan to have exams or integrate certification into the learning process though.

2.2.4 Learning paths

Depending on the modules' and chapters' settings learners can master a subject in sequential and non-sequential learning paths. SPEAR will as a default use non-sequential learning paths. Administrators and lecturers will set up the sections in a non-sequential way, so that the content can be completed in any order and allow the user to freely choose the content s/he would like to access.

2.2.5 Monitoring

Administrators and lecturers can easily track course progress on the Control Panel and the Lecturer Dashboard respectively. Charts showing statistical information filtered by custom criteria are available for administrators/lecturers and can be exported to Excel. As an example, the data can provide information about the geographical location of the participants, gender, completion status, chapter/module usage etc. Moreover, users' individual progress can also be tracked. Learners can contact the lecturers of the respective sections if they need further clarification on the subject covered by the section. When they use the online form, the system will send an automatic email to the assigned lecturer.

2.2.6 Evaluation

As a motivation, learners, as they progress, get various badges of achievement that are listed on their profile (e.g. when the system recognises excellent performance or strong participation).

2.2.7 Discussions and feedbacks

The system provides a platform for discussions related to the sections allowing learners to contact instructors and other learners completing the same section. Published presentations and the section itself can be rated by the users on a five-point scale. The average score is displayed on the platform informing the learners about the quality of content. Learners can directly send their feedbacks to instructors without it being published on the platform.

2.2.8 Reporting

Reporting module is available for administrators on the Control Panel where statistical indicators can be tracked and filtered. Scheduled (daily/weekly/monthly) reports can be set up that are sent by email.

2.2.9 In summary

nStructor complies with the following criteria beneficial for SPEAR:

- It has a responsive design (responsive design platforms should be able to adapt to any device or browser)
- It will give a variety of digital learning tools
- It will be managed and accessed fully online, there is no need to download or install the system to the users' computers
- It has a built-in assessment and tracking functionalities
- It has the ability to build incentives and rewards in the tracking learning progress
- It could connect the training material available online with the interactive LinkedIn discussions and give access to offered webinars
- It is SCORM (industry standard for E-learning interoperability) compliant

However,

- This LMS is not an Open Source system with a good developer’s community, but a commercial development of EMG Group (Europa Media) that has the flexibility of tailored customisation
- The platform cannot be integrated into other websites, including DG RTD, however, the full content of the courses can be integrated into any other website or E-learning platform solutions thanks to its compliancy with the necessary standards.

2.3 Design

The design of the website has been developed in line with the project’s logo and visual identity (including colour codes, graphic elements, project logo and fonts). Figure 2 showcases the layout of the “Home” section, the first page that is viewed by visiting users.

Figure 2: SPEAR Website “Home”

Moreover, the web-portal has been developed with a Responsive Web Design (RWD) which provides easy reading and navigation across a wide range of devices (from mobile phones to desktop computer monitors as shown in Figure 3) with a minimum requirement of resizing, panning, and scrolling.

The SPEAR Website meets the EU requirements on how to use cookies¹.

Figure 3 – Screenshot of the website policy on Cookies

Cookies policy

Cookies are small text files stored on users' computer by their browser. They have many applications, such as: tracking users as they navigate around a website; remembering user preferences; auto-logins for visitors coming back to a site; and website security. Website cookies policy was automatically implemented to the SPEAR website.

2.4 Open publication

Learning materials published on SPEAR's website (gathered from its blog and CoL sessions) will be available for use with the permission and reference to SPEAR (or specifically the authors) using Creative Common Licences. It may also be distributed on online education resource-gathering portals suitable for distributing material concerning GEP implementation. Virtual learning materials will be publicly available on GenPORT and EIGE's virtual platform.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/ipg/basics/legal/cookies/index_en.htm

3. Structure of the website

3.1 Menu

The Website visitors can find information about the project's objectives, activities, expected impact, target groups, Advisory Group and about the project partners. Visitors can follow up project related events and news, as well as gender equality and research related news and events. They can also have access to the publicly available project results or documents and other relevant documentation, in the download section.

With the above in mind, the following figure presents the menu structure of the SPEAR website.

Figure 4: Menu Structure of the website

This is the current menu structure of the SPEAR Website:

HOME

ABOUT

- About SPEAR
- Partners
- Advisory Group

NEWS&EVENTS

RESOURCES

- Publications
- Deliverables
- Presentations
- Videos
- Policy Recommendations
- Other useful documents

OTHER INITIATIVES

BLOG

LEARNING REPOSITORY

On the bottom of each page the following information is visible.

Figure 5: Menu Structure of the website - Footer

Terms of Use, Privacy Policy and Cookies Policy are the standard policies for a project website. When logged in, the editors and administrators of the website can access the Partner Area and the Control Panel to edit the website content. They can also log out from the system.

When the website visitors are not logged in they see the following in the Footer area:

[Terms of use](#) [Privacy policy](#) [Cookies policy](#) ➔

To access the Intranet, visitors need to have username and password to be able to log in. All partners receive access to Partner Area, but only selected people will have access to the Control Panel to be able to edit the content of the website or the Learning Repository.

3.3 Intranet

3.3.1 Partner Area

The Partner Area is used by the consortium to upload, manage and archive internal documents that are confidential and only accessible to partner organisations.

This area of the Intranet serves only as a document archiving system. Active communication between the partner organisations can be managed through the closed section of the Learning Repository.

Figure 6: SPEAR Partner Area

3.3.2 Control Panel

The Control Panel section of the website (single login/single authentication with the Partner Area) serves administrative and editorial purposes. It is protected by password, accessible only to project partners (see Figure 6) and was created with the objective of sharing the editorial duties and enabling the dissemination work leaders and the coordinator of the project to access and edit the content of the website. The same access and authentication process give access also to the closed learning repository.

Figure 6: SPEAR Login

When logged in, the website's content is available through the left menu (see Figure 7). The Articles button leads the user to the main content menu (About SPEAR; Patnrs; Blog, etc.) where the main content of the pages can be edited by those people who have received Administrator rights.

Figure 7: Intranet section of the website – Main content pages

Additional menu items lead to Blog or News, Events upload sections on the website.

Figure 8: Intranet section of the website – Blog editing

In this way, SPEAR partners can access the content of the website's pages and upload/edit the information, blog posts, useful documents for users, etc.

3.4 Repository

3.4.1 Forum for the Learning Support Clusters (LSCs) – SPEAR's internal repository

SPEAR repository supports the LSCs with the following functionalities: 1) a communal discussion forum/ blackboard serving a discussion space for each cluster; 2) document sharing platform that is easy to use – i.e., upload to and download from.

CO-AD members (S/IPs) have administrator roles and the Implementing Partners are users.

Figure 9: LSC Home Page

In order to protect confidentiality and openness within the clusters, an LSC cluster area is only accessible by its three members. Material to be opened up for anyone else must be agreed by all members of the LSC.

When an Implementing Partner enters the LSC area, they will be automatically guided to a different Home Page. For them only their own cluster is visible, and the Discussion Area will be the starting page.

In each page of the LSC area, there is a direct link to the Learning Repository as well.

Figure 10: Entering the LSC – Discussion Area

LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER

Discussion Area Document Area

LEARNING REPOSITORY

DISCUSSION AREA

SDU

TOPICS

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Lorem ipsum Lorem ipsum

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Lorem ipsum Lorem ipsum

DISCUSSIONS

Date of publication	Date of last post	Topic of the last	Author name	Tags Keyword	Posts
03.07.19	03.05.18	Gender Equality	Harry Potter	Abrakadabra	3
03.07.19	03.05.18	Gender Equality	Harry Potter	Abrakadabra	3
03.07.19	03.05.18	Gender Equality	Harry Potter	Abrakadabra	3
03.07.19	03.05.18	Gender Equality	Harry Potter	Abrakadabra	3

+ CREATE NEW TOPIC

Author: Eva Sophia Myers
03 January 2019

Something of SPEAR

SPEAR (Supporting and Implementing Plans for gender Equality in Academia and Research) is a Coordination and Support Action project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS)

Reply

CREATE NEW TOPIC

Date of publication

Date of last post

Author name

Topic of the text

Tags Keyword

Posts

Lorem ipsum

Create

Figure 11: LSC Document Area

3.4.2 Learning Repository – public part

The Learning Repository will provide access to digital learning material primarily targeting change agents at Research Performing Organisations. The objective is to provide supporting and learning material for the steps of EIGE’s GEAR Tool and GEP Implementation. The digital content will be based on the presentations, discussions, exercises and material provided in SPEAR’s Communities of Learning workshops that take place at SPEAR’s Project Learning and Support Meetings as well as developed virtual learning sessions.

The learning material developed in SPEAR will be organised and uploaded online within WP2 as part of SPEAR’s dissemination activities. All recordings featuring SPEAR partners used in virtual learning material (e.g., webinars) will be recorded with the consent of the participants.

Most of the e-learning material will be created with the help of Articulate Storyline software using the training material of the in-vivo sessions. EM will be responsible for the e-learning transformation. The digital content will include a combination of different elements such as presentations with supporting files (teaching notes, articles, reports, materials for further reading), case studies, videos, tutorials and interactive elements (tests and quizzes).

The content will be organised in specific topics and EIGE’s GEP Implementation steps. All content will be searchable based on the CoL workshop dates, EIGE’s GEP Implementation steps

as well as based on specific keywords that will be tagged to the content.

The content developed will be SCORM compliant and thus can be integrated in any other platform, such as GenPORT or EIGE's virtual platform.

Figure 12: Learning Repository Home Page

The screenshot shows the SPEAR Learning Repository Home Page. At the top, there is a header with the SPEAR logo on the left and the text 'LEARNING REPOSITORY' on the right. Below the header is a dark blue navigation bar with four links: 'Home', 'GEP Implementation', 'My profile', and 'Control Panel'. To the right of the navigation bar is a teal button labeled 'LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER'. Below the navigation bar is a section titled 'INTRODUCTION'. The introduction text states: 'SPEAR will present its learning materials in an attractive, user-friendly manner that allows feedback publishing and other interactions. Under the learning repository a comprehensive collection of teaching and learning materials will be made accessible, used throughout the implementation of the gender equality plans at the Implementing Organisations of SPEAR. SPEAR will work on an agreement with GenPORT to integrate SPEAR's platform and learning material to their site as well.' Below the introduction text is a link labeled 'link to tutorial'. To the right of the introduction text is a decorative graphic of a stylized flame or leaf. Below the introduction text are two columns of content. The left column is titled 'GEP IMPLEMENTATION STEPS' and contains a list of five steps: 'Step 0 Getting started', 'Step 1 Analysing and assessing the state-of-play in the institution', 'Step 2 Setting up a Gender Equality Plan', 'Step 3 Implementing a Gender Equality Plan', 'Step 4 Monitoring progress and evaluating a Gender Equality Plan', and 'Step 5 What comes after the Gender Equality Plan?'. The right column is titled 'GENDER EQUALITY TOPICS' and contains a list of two topics: '1 Gender and Equality' and '2 Gender Equality in Academia'. At the bottom of the page is a search bar with a magnifying glass icon and the text 'Search Keyword'.

Figure 13: Learning Repository – Module level page

Home
GEP Implementation
My profile
Controll Panel

LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER

GEP STEP 0
GETTING STARTED

What our participants think

★
★
★
☆
☆

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DISCUSSIONS

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COMMENT

GENDER EQUALITY TOPICS

Gender and Equality

🕒 23:40

Gender Equality in Academia

🕒 15:30

Next topic

🕒 18:05

CONTACT THE EXPERT

Send question directly to gender equality expert and get an answer by e-mail.

Your Comment

Send

Figure 14: Learning Repository – Chapter Level page

LEARNING REPOSITORY

Home
GEP Implementation
My profile
Control Panel

LEARNING SUPPORT CLUSTER

TOPIC #1	TOPIC TITLE
<p>What our participants think</p> <p>★ ★ ★ ☆ ☆</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi enim erat, efficitur vitae felis a, ultricesperet aliquam nunc. Etiam tincidunt consectetur nunc non molestie. Duis aliquet vulputate tortor, ut laculis libero. Nam ut euismod turpis. Morbi arcu arcu, auctor in eros sit amet, scelerisque convallis.</p>

DISCUSSIONS

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LEARNING MATERIAL

Audio video presentation

23:45

Video

15:30

Podcast

18:25

Quiz

18:25

Blog post

COMMENT

Your Comment

Publish

CONTACT THE EXPERT

Send question directly to gender equality expert and get an answer by e-mail.

Your Comment

Send

ATTACHMENTS

Word file

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4. Monitoring

Continuous monitoring of the website traffic is ensured by engaging Google Analytics. Different types of data can be monitored and recorded during the project lifetime in order to receive statistics for its further development, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 15: SPEAR Google Analytics – User profile page

The data on the traffic of the SPEAR website as collected through Google Analytics will feed into the framework developed for monitoring the communication and dissemination activities of the project.

5. Future Developments

The SPEAR website, which has been developed by Europa Media, will be continuously developed and updated, to ensure the provision of up-to-date information to its visitors. Europa Media, with the help of all SPEAR partners, will be responsible for this task and will guarantee continuous access to the web-portal during as well as after the end of the project.

Moreover, within the framework of SPEAR, several sessions of training material developments - transformation of content into virtual learning material - will be completed and then integrated into the learning repository of the project. This will happen as the project unfolds and the learning material is developed.

As *nJinn* and *nStructor* are the property of Europa Media, and exclusively developed in house, additional functionalities can be programmed and integrated into the website or the Learning Repository if and where relevant and needed.